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**ESTIMATION OF SUB-WATERSHED WISE MORPHOMETRIC
PARAMETERS OF HAROHALLI WATERSHED**

Nanjundi.P¹, Dr.M.Inayathulla², Sandhya M. C³

Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, NMIT, Bangalore-560064.Karnataka, India.

Associate Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, UVCE, Bangalore-560056.Karnataka, India.

ME student in Department of Civil Engineering, UVCE, Bangalore -560056.Karnataka, India.

Abstract

Morphometric analysis and prioritization of eleven sub-watersheds of Harohalli valley, located in Kanakapura Taluk, Ramanagera District, Karnataka state, India is carried out using Remote Sensing and GIS techniques. The morphometric parameters considered for analysis are stream order, stream length, bifurcation ratio, drainage density, stream frequency, texture ratio, form factor, circulatory ratio, elongation ratio, relief ratio, length of overland flow and basin shape. . The elongation ratio ranges from 0.38 to 0.71 which indicates that the watershed is more elongated to elongate. The values of relief vary from 914 m to 667 m indicates that the watershed has enough slope for the runoff to occur from the remote point of the watershed to mouth. The relative relief ratios are ranging from 0.001 to 0.007. In the present case the values of Bifurcation ratio varies from 2.73 to 5.3 for the sub watersheds and for the sub watershed 1 the bifurcation ratio is more than 5 hence it shows there is a geological disturbance. The watershed has a dendritic drainage pattern. The bifurcation ratio varies from 2.73 to 5.3 and all sub-watersheds fall under normal basin category. The compound parameter values are calculated and prioritization rating of eleven sub-watersheds in Harohalli valley was carried out. The sub-watershed with lowest compound parameter value is given the highest priority. The sub-watershed 3 is likely to be subjected to maximum soil erosion hence it should be provided with immediate soil conservation measures.

Keywords - Dendrites', Drainage Patterns, GIS, Morphometric analysis, Sub watershed

Introduction

Watershed is a natural hydrological entity from which runoff resulting from precipitation flows past a single point into large stream, river, lake or ocean. Thus, a watershed is the surface area drained by a part or the totality of one or several given water courses and can be taken as a basic erosional

landscape element where land and water resources interact in a perceptible manner. Though a catchment and watershed are same by definition, the term 'catchment' is often used to refer that area which drains into a reservoir and the area in the downstream of a reservoir which is irrigated using water from the

same is termed as the command area (Sebastian et al., 1995).Morphometric analysis provides quantitative description of the basin geometry to understand initial slope or inequalities in the rock hardness, structural controls, recent diastrophism, geological and geomorphic history of drainage basin (Strahler, 1964). Morphometric analysis requires measurement of linear features, gradient of channel network and contributing ground slopes of the drainage basin. Morphometry is the measurement and mathematical analysis of the configuration of the earth's surface, shape and dimension of its landforms. A major emphasis in geomorphology over the past several decades has been on the development of quantitative physiographic methods to describe the evolution and behavior of surface drainage networks (Horton, 1945). Most previous morphometric analyses were based on arbitrary areas or individual channel segments. Using watershed as a basic unit in morphometric analysis is the most logical choice. In fact, they are the fundamental units of the fluvial landscape and a great amount of research has focused on their geometric characteristics, including the topology of the stream networks and quantitative description of drainage texture, pattern and shape. The morphometric characteristics at the watershed scale may contain important information regarding its formation and development because all hydrologic and geomorphic processes occur within the watershed (Singh, 1992).

The quantitative analysis of morphometric parameters is found to be of immense utility in river basin evaluation, watershed prioritization for soil and water conservation and natural resources management at watershed level. Morphometric analysis of a watershed provides a quantitative description of the drainage system which is an important aspect of the characterization of watersheds (Strahler, 1964). The influence of drainage morphometry is very significant in understanding the landform processes, soil physical properties and erosional characteristics. Drainage characteristics of many river basins and sub basins in different parts of the globe have been studied using conventional methods (Horton, 1945; Strahler, 1957, 1964). Geographical Information System (GIS) techniques are now a day used for assessing various terrain and morphometric parameters of the drainage basins and watersheds, as they provide a flexible environment and a powerful tool for the manipulation and analysis of spatial information. In the present study stream number, order, frequency, density and bifurcation ratio are derived and tabulated on the basis of areal and linear properties of drainage channels using GIS based on drainage lines as represented over the topographical maps (scale 1:50,000).

The quantitative morphometric analysis of the drainage basin is considered to be the most satisfactory method because it enables us:

- i. To understand the relationship between different aspects of the drainage pattern of the same drainage basin;
- ii. For comparative evaluation of different drainage basins developed in various geologic and climatic regimes and
- iii. To define certain useful parameters of drainage basins in numerical terms.

Remote sensing and Geographical Information System (GIS) techniques have already been used for assessing various terrain and morphometric parameters of the drainage basins and watersheds, as they provide a flexible environment and a powerful tool for the manipulation and analysis of spatial information particularly for the feature identification and the extraction of information for better understanding. In the present study, the GIS analysis techniques were used to evaluate linear, relief and aerial morphometric parameters of the sub-watersheds for the future developmental planning of the watersheds.

In this chapter, morphometric analysis of Harohalli watershed is carried out at sub watershed level using GIS which is a suitable tool to study the morphological analysis. The entire watershed was divided into 11 sub watersheds based on topography and drainage pattern. The analysis was carried out through measurement of linear, aerial and relief aspects of watershed. The morphometric parameters were useful in understanding the hydrological processes of the drainage basin

1.2 Linear Aspects

Linear aspects include the measurements of linear features of drainage such as stream order, stream length, stream length ratio, bifurcation ratio, length of overland flow and drainage pattern.

1.2.1 Stream order

The stream order is a measure of degree of stream branching within a watershed. In the drainage basin analysis the first step is to determine the stream orders. In the present study, the channel segment of the drainage basin has been ranked according to Strahler's stream ordering system. According to Strahler (1964), the smallest fingertip tributaries are designated as order 1. Where two first order channels join, a channel segment of order 2 is formed; Where two of order 2 joins, a segment of order 3 is formed; and so forth. The trunk stream through which all discharge of water and sediment passes is therefore the stream segment of highest order. Fig 1.1 shows the stream order map of Harohalli watershed.

Fig. 1.1 Stream order map of Harohalli watershed

1.2.2 Bifurcation ratio

The term bifurcation ratio (R_b) may be defined as the ratio of the number of the stream segments N_u of given order to the number of segments of the next higher order $N_{(u+1)}$ (Schumn, 1956). Horton (1945) considered the bifurcation ratio as an index of relief and dissections. Strahler (1957) demonstrated that bifurcation ratio shows a small range of variation for different regions or for different environment except where the powerful geological control dominates.

$$R_b = \frac{N_u}{N_{(u+1)}} \quad (1.1)$$

Where,

R_b = Bifurcation Ratio

N_u = Number of stream segments of order u

$N_{(u+1)}$ = Number of stream segments of order $(u+1)$

It is observed, the R_b is not same from one order to its next order. These irregularities are dependent upon the geological and lithological development of the drainage basin (Strahler, 1964). The lower values of R_b are characteristics of the sub-watersheds which have suffered less structural disturbances (Strahler, 1964) and the drainage patterns has not been distorted because of the structural disturbances. In the present study, the higher values of R_b indicates strong structural control on the drainage pattern while the lower values indicative of sub watersheds that are not affected by structural disturbances.

1.2.3 Stream length

Length of the stream is an indication of the contributing area of the watershed. The length of the stream is an indication of the steepness of the drainage basin as well as the degree of drainage. Steep well drained areas generally have numerous small tributaries; whereas, in plains, where soils are deep and permeable, only relatively long tributaries (generally perennial streams) will be in existence. This factor thus gives the idea of the efficiency of the drainage network.

Stream length is one of the most significant hydrological features of the watershed as it reveals surface runoff characteristics streams of relatively smaller lengths are characteristics of areas with larger slopes and finer textures. Longer lengths of streams are generally indicative of flatter gradients. Generally, the total length of stream segments is maximum in first order streams and decreases as the stream order increases. The number of streams of various orders in the basin are counted and their lengths from mouth to drainage divide are measured with the help of GIS software. Plot of the logarithm of stream length versus stream order shows the linear pattern which indicates the homogenous rock material subjected to weathering erosion characteristics of the watershed. Deviation from its general behavior indicates that the terrain is characterized by variation in lithology and topography.

1.2.4 Mean stream length

Mean stream length (L_{sm}) is a characteristic property related to the drainage network components and its associated watershed surfaces (Strahler, 1964). This has been calculated by dividing the total stream length of order (u) by the number of streams of segments in that order. The deviation might be due to change in topographic elevation and slope of the basin.

$$L_{sm} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N L_u}{N_u} \quad (1.2)$$

Where,

L_{sm} = mean stream length of order u

L_u = total stream length of order u

N_u = total number of stream segments of order u

1.2.5 Stream length ratio

Stream length ratio (RL) is the ratio of the mean length of the one order to the next order of the stream segments. Total stream length of a given order is inversely related to stream order, i.e., total stream length decreases from the lower order to the successively higher orders. This change might be attributed to variation in slope and topography, indicating the youth stage of geomorphic development in the streams of the study area (Singh and Singh, 1997 and Vittala et al., 2004).

$$R_l = \frac{L_u}{L_{(u-1)}} \quad (1.3)$$

Where,

R_l = Stream length ratio

L_u = mean stream length of order u

$L_{(u-1)}$ = mean stream length of the next lower order $u-1$

1.2.6 Length of over land flow

Length of overland flow is the flow of water over the surface before it becomes concentrated in definite stream channels. The length of overland flow is a measure of erodibility, and is one of the independent variable affecting both the hydrologic and physiographic development of the drainage basin.

Surface runoff follows a system of down slope flow paths from the drainage divide (basin perimeter) to the nearest channel. This flow net, comprising a family of orthogonal curves with respect to the topographic contours, locally converges or diverges from parallelism, depending upon position in the basin. Horton defined the length of overland flow " L_o " as the length of flow path, projected to a horizontal of the rain flow from a point on the drainage divide to a point on the adjacent stream channel. " L_o " is approximately equal to one half of the reciprocal of the drainage density. The shorter the length of overland flow, the quicker the surface runoff from the streams.

1.2.7 Drainage Pattern

The drainage pattern is an indicator of landforms and bedrock type and also suggests soil characteristics and site drainage condition. The drainage pattern is the planimetric arrangement of stream engraved into the land surface by a drainage system. The aggregate of drainage ways establish a design on the earth's surface, adjusted to topographic, structural and lithological controls. The drainage pattern may reflect original slope, original structure, or the modification of the earth surface, including uplift depression, tilting and other structural elements like faulting, folding, warping and jointing. The drainage pattern of the study is dendritic.

1.3 Areal Aspects

Area of a watershed (A) and perimeter (P) are the important parameters in quantitative morphology. The area of the watershed is defined as the total area projected upon a horizontal plane contributing to cumulate of all order of watersheds. Perimeter is the length of the boundary of the watershed which can be drawn from topographical maps. Watershed area is hydrologically important because it directly affects the size of the storm hydrograph and the magnitudes of peak and mean runoff. It is interesting that the maximum flood discharge per unit area is inversely related to size (Chorley et al., 1957).

Areal aspects “ A_u ” of a watershed of given order ‘ u ’ is defined as the total area projected upon a horizontal plane contributing overland flow to the channel segment of the given order and includes all tributaries of lower order. It comprises of watershed shape factor, form factor, circularity ratio, elongation ratio and drainage density.

1.3.1 Watershed shape factor

Watershed shape is the shape of projected surface on the horizontal plane of watershed map. The watershed shape has a significant effect on stream discharge characteristic for example; the elongated watershed having a high bifurcation ratio can be expected to have alternated flood discharge. But on the other hand, the round or circular watershed with a low bifurcation ratio may have a sharp flood discharge.

The shape of a watershed has a profound influence on the runoff and sediment transport process. The shape of the drainage basin also governs the rate at which water enters the stream. The quantitative expression of watershed can be characterized by form factor, compaction coefficient, circularity ratio, and elongation ratio.

1.3.2 Form factor

Form factor (R_f) may be defined as the ratio of the area of the watershed and square of the watershed length (Horton, 1932) and is expressed as

$$R_f = \frac{A}{L^2} \quad (1.4)$$

Where,

R_f = Form factor

A = area of the watershed (Sq.km)

L = watershed length (km)

The value of form factor would always be greater than 0.78 for a perfectly circular watershed. Smaller the value of the form factor, more elongated will be the watershed. The watershed with high form factors have high peak flows of shorter duration, whereas elongated watershed with low form factor ranges from 0.54 indicating them to be elongated in shape and flow for longer duration

1.3.3 Compactness coefficient

According to Gravelius (1914) compactness coefficient of a watershed is the ratio of perimeter of watershed to circumference of circular area, which equals the area of the watershed. Compactness coefficient is used to express the relationship of a hydrologic watershed with that of a circular watershed having the same area as the hydrologic watershed. The C_c is independent of size of watershed and dependent only on the slope. A circular watershed is the most hazardous from a drainage stand point because it will yield the shortest time of concentration before peak flow occurs in the watershed.

$$Compactness\ coefficient = \frac{P}{2\sqrt{\pi A}} \quad (1.5)$$

Where,

P = perimeter of the watershed (km)

A = area of the watershed (Sq.km)

An index of shape factor as defined by Horton (1945) is the reciprocal of the form factor given by,

$$S_f = \frac{L^2}{A} \quad (1.6)$$

Where,

S_f = watershed shape factor

L = total length of watershed (km)

A = total area of watershed (Sq.km)

1.3.4 Circularity ratio

The circulatory ratio is mainly concerned with the length and frequency of streams, geological structures, land use/land cover, climate, relief and slope of the basin. It is the ratio of the area of the watersheds to the area of circle having the same circumference as the perimeter of the watershed.

$$R_c = \frac{4\pi A}{P^2} \tag{1.7}$$

Where,

R_c = Circularity ratio

A = watershed area (Sq.km)

P = perimeter of watershed (km)

The value ranges from 0.2 to 0.5, greater the value more is the circularity ratio. It is the significant ratio which indicates the stage of dissection in the study region. Its low, medium and high values are correlated with youth, mature and old stage of the cycle of the tributary watershed of the region.

1.3.5 Elongation ratio

Schumm (1956) used an elongation ratio (R_e) defined as the ratio of diameter of a circle of the same area as the watershed to the maximum watershed length. It is a very significant index in the analysis of watershed shape which helps to give an idea about the hydrological character of a drainage basin.

$$R_e = \frac{2\sqrt{A}/\pi}{L} \tag{1.8}$$

Where,

R_e = Elongation ratio

A = watershed area (Sq.km)

L = length of the watershed (km)

The value of R_e ranges from 0.4 to 1, lesser value more is the elongation of the watershed. Strahler states the ratio runs between 0.6-1 over a wide variety of climatic and geologic types. Values of 1 are found in typical regions of low relief, while values from 0.6-0.8 are generally associated with strong relief and steep ground slopes. The following (Table 1.1) shows the watershed shape ratio and its interface.

Table 1.1 Watershed shape ratio and its interface

Watershed	Shape ratio
Circular	0.9
Oval	0.8-0.9
Less elongated	0.7-0.8
Elongated	0.5-0.7
More elongated	0.5

average length of stream channel for the whole basin. It has been observed from drainage density measurements made over a wide range of geologic and climatic types that a low drainage density is more likely to occur in regions of highly resistant or highly permeable subsoil material under dense

vegetative cover, and where relief is low. High drainage density is the resultant of weak or impermeable subsurface material, sparse vegetation and mountainous relief. Low drainage density leads to coarse drainage texture while high drainage density leads to fine drainage texture (Strahler, 1964). The low value of drainage density influences greater infiltration and hence the wells in this region will have good water potential leading to higher specific capacity of wells. In the areas of higher drainage density the infiltration is less and surface runoff is more. The drainage density can also indirectly indicated groundwater potential of an area, due to its surface runoff and permeability. Table shows the drainage density and its texture.

1.3.6 Drainage density

Drainage density is the other element of drainage analysis which provides a better quantitative expression to the dissection and analysis of land forms, although a function of climate, lithology, structures and relief history of the region and can ultimately be used as an indirect indicator to explain those variables, as well as the morphogenesis of landform. It is the ratio of total channel segment lengths cumulated for all orders within a basin to the basin area, which is expressed in terms of m/sq. m or km/sq. km. Drainage density (D_d) is one of the important indications of the linear scale of landform elements in stream eroded topography. It is defined as the total stream length to the total area of watershed. The drainage density is expressed as km/Sq.km. It gives the mean length of the stream within the watershed per unit area. Drainage density varies inversely with the length of the overland flow, and therefore, provides at least some indication of the drainage efficiency of the watershed. Drainage density is mathematically expressed as

$$D_d = \frac{\sum L_u}{A} \tag{1.9}$$

Where,

D_d = Drainage density (km/km²)

$\sum L_u$ = total stream length of all orders (km)

A = area of watershed (Sq.km)

The drainage density indicates the closeness of spacing of channels, thus providing a quantitative measure of the

Table 1.2 Drainage density for different textures

Drainage density (km/Sq. km)	Textures
< 1.24	Very coarse
1.24-2.49	Coarse
2.49-3.73	Moderate
3.73-4.97	Fine
> 4.97	Very fine

1.3.7 Constant of channel maintenance

The inverse of drainage density is the constant of channel maintenance (Schumm, 1956). It indicates the number of Sq.km of watershed required to sustain one linear km of channel and expressed as Sq. km/km.

$$C = \frac{1}{D_d} \tag{1.10}$$

It not only depends on rock type permeability, climatic regime, vegetation, relief but also as the duration of erosion and climatic history. The constant is extremely low in areas of close dissection.

1.3.8 Stream frequency

Horton (1932) introduced stream frequency (Fs) or channel frequency which is the total number of stream segments of all orders per unit area. Hypothetically, it is possible to have the basin of same drainage density differing in stream frequency and basins of same stream frequency differing in drainage density.

$$S_f = \frac{N_s}{A} \tag{1.11}$$

Where,

S_f =Stream frequency

N_s = number of streams

A = area of the watershed (Sq.km)

Table 4.3 shows the stream frequency for No. of streams/Sq. km and the inference can be drawn for the study area.

Table 4.3 Stream frequency for No. of streams/Sq. km

Stream Frequency	No. streams/Sq. km
Low	0-5
Moderate	5-10
Moderate high	10-15
High	15-20
Very high	20-25

1.4 Relief Aspects

Relief aspects of drainage basin relate to the three dimensional features of the basin involving area, volume and altitude of vertical dimension of landforms where in different morphometric

methods are used to analyse terrain characteristics. Relief is the elevation difference between the highest and lowest point on the valley floor of the region. Relief aspects is an indicator of flow direction of water as it is an important factor in understanding the extent of denudational process that have undergone within the watershed. It comprises of Watershed relief, Relief ratio, Relative relief, Ruggedness number.

1.4.1 Watershed relief

Difference in the elevation between the highest point of a watershed and the lowest point on the valley floor is known as the total relief of the river watershed. The relief ratio may be defined as the ratio between the total relief of a watershed and the longest dimension of the watershed parallel to the main drainage line (Schumm, 1956). Low value of relief ratios are mainly due to the resistant basement rocks of the basin and low degree of slope.

The highest elevation in the watershed is found to be 914 m above the mean sea level at the remote point of the watershed and the lowest elevation is 667 m above the mean sea level at the mouth of the watershed. The overall relief calculated for the watershed is 0.247 km.

1.4.2 Relief ratio

The elevation difference between the highest and lowest points on the valley floor of a subwatershed is known as the total relief of that subwatershed. The relief ratio (Rh) of maximum relief to horizontal distance along the longest dimension of the watershed parallel to the principal drainage line is termed as relief ratio. There is also a correlation between hydrological characteristics and the relief ratio of a drainage basin. The Rh normally increases with decreasing drainage area and size of sub-watersheds of a given drainage basin. It is noticed that high values of Rh indicate steep slope and high relief (m),

while the lower values may indicate presence of basement rocks that are exposed in the form of small ridges and mounds with lower degree of slope.

$$R_f = \frac{H}{L} \tag{1.13}$$

Where, H = total watershed relief (km), L = maximum length of the watershed (km)

1.4.3 Relative relief

Relative relief is defined as the ratio of the maximum watershed relief to the perimeter of the watershed. It is computed as

$$R_r = \frac{H}{P} \tag{1.14}$$

Where, R_r = Relative relief, H= maximum relief (km), P = perimeter of the basin (km)

1.4.4 Ruggedness number

Strahler’s (1968) ruggedness number is the product of the watershed relief and the drainage density and usefully combines slope steepness with its length. The low ruggedness value of watershed implies that area is less prone to soil erosion and have intrinsic structural complexity in association with relief and drainage density. High values of the Ruggedness number in the watershed are because both the variables like relief and drainage density are enlarged. Extensively high value of ruggedness number occurs for a high relief region with high stream density.

$$R_n = \frac{HD_d}{1000} \tag{1.15}$$

It is computed as R_n = Ruggedness number, H = watershed relief (m), D_d = drainage density (km/Sq.km)

Table 1.4 and 1.5 shows the watershed wise morphometric characteristics and parameters respectively of Harohalli watershed. A fig 1.2, 1.3 shows the regression of stream order on number of stream segments of the Harohalli watershed. Figs 1.4, 1.5 shows watershed wise regression of stream order on mean stream length of Harohalli watershed.

Table 1.4 Sub watershed wise morphometric characteristics of Harohalli

WS No.	Area No. (Sq. Km)	Total No. of Segments	Total Length (Km)	Highest Stream Order	Stream Order. 1		Stream Order. 2		Stream Order. 3		Stream Order. 4		Stream Order. 5		Stream Order. 6	
					No.	Length (Km)										
1	15.51	34	30.17	3	28	17.61	5	8.91	1	3.65	-	-	-	-	-	-
2	15.97	59	44.83	4	44	27.63	12	7.07	2	6.71	1	3.42	-	-	-	-
3	37.07	122	108.07	5	92	57.33	17	15.09	7	17.88	5	12.5	1	5.27	-	-
4	37.27	147	108.24	5	109	66.84	26	19.85	9	8.27	2	9.21	1	4.07	-	-
5	21.47	89	58.11	4	70	35.12	13	11.84	5	3.68	1	7.47	-	-	-	-
6	27.16	36	71.08	6	25	22.56	6	8.63	1	2.22	1	7.47	2	9.35	1	20.85
7	30.02	79	71.32	6	56	30.25	18	12.16	4	8.06	-	-	-	-	1	20.85
8	13.38	54	34.44	4	42	20.46	8	7.79	2	5.9	2	0.29	-	-	-	-
9	19.36	59	47.99	4	46	28.38	10	10.34	2	4.37	1	4.9	-	-	-	-
10	20.98	70	49.8	4	51	26.61	13	13.15	4	5.24	2	4.8	-	-	-	-
11	43.25	117	112.9	6	86	51.34	20	16.99	4	11.47	6	12.25	-	-	1	20.85

Table 1.5 Sub-Watershed wise morphometric parameters of Harohalli watershed

Sl No.	Watershed Parameters	Units	Watershed number				
			1	2	3	4	5
1	Watershed area	km ²	15.61	15.97	37.07	37.27	21.47
2	Perimeter of the watershed	km	17.34	15.99	31.47	26.83	21.59
3	Maximum length of the watershed	km	5.29	4.31	9.78	8.33	7.09
4	Maximum width of the watershed	km	5.17	5.62	7.95	7.82	4.56
5	Watershed highest stream order	No.	3	4	5	5	4
6	Cumulative stream segments	No.	34	59	122	147	89
7	Cumulative stream length	km	30.17	44.83	108.07	108.24	58.11
8	Length of overland flow	km	0.26	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.18
9	Drainage density	km/km ²	1.93	2.81	2.92	2.9	2.71
10	Constant of channel maintenance	km ² /km	0.52	0.36	0.34	0.34	0.37
11	Stream frequency	No/ km ²	2.18	3.69	3.29	3.94	4.15
12	Bifurcation ratio		5.3	3.89	3.56	3.4	4.33
14	Form factor		0.56	0.86	0.39	0.54	0.43
15	Shape factor		1.79	1.16	2.58	1.86	2.34
16	Circularity ratio		0.65	0.79	0.47	0.65	0.58
17	Elongation ratio		0.47	0.59	0.4	0.47	0.42
18	Compactness coefficient		1.24	1.13	1.46	1.24	1.31
19	Total watershed relief	km	0.097	0.076	0.041	0.018	0.129
20	Relief ratio		0.0183	0.0176	.0042	0.0022	0.0182
21	Relative relief		0.006	0.005	0.001	0.001	0.006
22	Ruggedness number		0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.003

Sl No.	Watershed Parameters	Units	Watershed number					
			6	7	8	9	10	11
1	Watershed area	km ²	27.16	30.02	13.38	19.36	20.98	43.25
2	Perimeter of the watershed	km	22.3	25.45	17.8	20.06	20.22	39.28
3	Maximum length of the watershed	km	4.7	5.34	6.03	7.46	6.33	7.96
4	Maximum width of the watershed	km	7.54	6.76	2.79	3.16	4.46	9.15
5	Watershed highest stream order	No.	6	6	4	4	4	6
6	Cumulative stream segments	No.	36	79	54	59	70	117
7	Cumulative stream length	km	71.08	71.32	34.44	47.99	49.8	112.9
8	Length of overland flow	km	0.19	0.21	0.19	0.2	0.21	0.19
9	Drainage density	km/km ²	2.62	2.38	2.57	2.48	2.37	2.61
10	Constant of channel maintenance	km ² /km	0.38	0.42	0.39	0.4	0.42	0.38
11	Stream frequency	No/ km ²	1.33	2.63	4.04	3.05	3.34	2.71

12	Bifurcation ratio		2.73	3.87	3.42	3.87	3.06	3.99
13	Length ratio		2.32	4.86	1.69	2.01	1.69	3.93
14	Form factor		1.23	1.05	0.37	0.35	0.52	0.68
15	Shape factor		0.81	0.95	2.72	2.87	1.91	1.47
16	Circularity ratio		0.69	0.58	0.53	0.61	0.65	0.35
17	Elongation ratio		0.71	0.65	0.39	0.38	0.46	0.53
18	Compactness coefficient		1.21	1.31	1.37	1.29	1.25	1.68
19	Total watershed relief	km	0.093	0.048	0.119	0.12	0.041	0.033
20	Relief ratio		0.0197	0.0089	0.0197	0.016	0.0065	0.004
21	Relative relief		0.004	0.002	0.007	0.006	0.002	0.001
22	Ruggedness number		0.002	0.001	0.003	0.003	0.001	0.001

1.5 Results and Discussions

In order to analyze the different aspects of the watershed, quantitative morphometric analysis is carried out. Table 1.4 and 1.5 shows the various morphometric parameters estimated of all sub watersheds of Harohalli watershed.

In the present study, ranking of streams has been carried out based on the method proposed by Strahler (1964). According to Strahler's method of ordering, the highest stream order obtained was 6th order and hence designated as 6th order watershed. The watershed is divided into 11 watersheds depending upon the topography and the drainage pattern as per the watershed Atlas of India (1990). Out of the 11 watersheds, watershed number 1 is the 3rd order, watershed number 2, 5, 8, 9 and 10 are 4th order, watershed number 3 and 4 are 5th order and watershed number 6, 7 and 11 are 6th order.

The stream length has been computed based on the Horton's law for all the 11 watersheds. Generally the total length of stream segments is maximum in first order streams and decreases as the stream order increases in the present case. In order to check for the linearity, individual watershed graphs of stream order verses number of stream segments are plotted and is shown in the Figs. 1.2, 1.3. From these figures it is observed that in most of the watersheds there is a variation from general observation. This may be due to flowing of streams from high altitude, change in rock type and moderately steep slopes and probable uplift across the basin (Singh and Singh, 1997; Vittala et al., 2004 and Chopra et al., 2005).

Figs. 1.4, 1.5 shows the relationship between stream order and mean stream length as proposed by the Strahler's system of stream ordering for individual watersheds of Harohalli watershed area. Generally, it is observed that the mean stream length of any given order is greater than that of the lower order but less than that of the next higher order. But from these graphs it is seen that there is a variation in general observation. This deviation might be due to change in topographic elevation and structural disturbance.

The bifurcation ratio is a dimensional property and it ranges between 2 and 5 for watersheds in which the geologic structures do not distort the drainage pattern. Bifurcation ratio shows a small range of variation for different regions or for different environments except where the powerful geological control dominates (Strahler, 1957). It is observed from the Table 4.5 that the R_b is not same from one order to next order. These irregularities are dependent on the geological and lithological development of the watershed (Strahler, 1964). The lower values of R_b are characteristics of watersheds which have suffered less structural disturbances (Strahler, 1964) and drainage patterns has not been distorted because of structural disturbances (Nag, 1998). In the present case the values of R_b varies from 2.73 to 5.3 for the sub watersheds and for the sub watershed 1 the bifurcation ratio is more than 5 hence it shows there is a geological disturbance.

The drainage density reflects the land use, affects the infiltration and watershed response time between precipitation and discharge. The drainage density of the area varies from 1.93 to 2.92 km/km² indicating that the area is coarse texture.

The values of stream frequency for eleven watersheds exhibits positive correlation with the drainage density values of the area indicating the increase in stream population with respect to increase in drainage density. Stream frequency value for the watershed varies from 1.33 to 4.15 this indicates that the stream frequency is low.

The circularity ratio varies from 0.35 to 0.79 for the watersheds. Its low, medium and high values are correlated with youth, mature and old stage of the cycle of the tributary watershed of the region. The elongation ratio ranges from 0.38 to 0.71 which indicates that the watershed is more elongated to elongate.

The values of relief vary from 914 m to 667 m indicates that the watershed has enough slope for the runoff to occur from the remote point of the watershed to mouth. The relative relief ratios are ranging from 0.001 to 0.007. The high relative relief indicates that it is composed of resistant rock patches and low relief ratio indicates less resistant patch of rocks.

Also this study has demonstrated the use of morphometric analysis to understand the hydrological process of the watershed and to draw the influences from the quantification drainage characters and parameters on runoff and soil loss to suitable sites for conservation of natural resources available within the watershed area.

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